

**ENHANCING RELATIONSHIP DYNAMICS: THE IMPACT OF STRENGTHENING
TRUST, RESPECT, AND COMMUNICATION (TRRECO) IN LEO AND ANGELA'S
RELATIONSHIP**

A research paper presented to Ma. Angela C. Pineda

In partial fulfillment
for their Fourth Anniversary
as Leo's gift to his girlfriend, Angela

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Every romantic relationship has started somewhere, either from complete scratch, at a not-so-good point in time, or at the best moment of someone's life. For Leo, all had begun at a point he did not expect it to.

It all started in September 2019, when Leo experienced being in a rebound relationship with his supposed-to-be first girlfriend, who left him without a word or apology. Unfortunately for him, it was his last year in senior high school, and focusing on his studies was becoming increasingly difficult. So he made every effort to move on from her, knowing that staying in such a devastating situation and grieving for an extended period could impact his studies.

Almost a week later, during the school's intramurals, a Grade 11 student he only knew by the name of Angela requested for them to have a picture. Although he did not know her personally, Leo did not hesitate. A picture of them was then taken and, unbeknownst to Leo, it would mark the start of their undying love for one another.

Then, it was because of the picture that, on the same day after school, Leo was informed that Angela had been long since admiring him. However, because he didn't really know her at the time, Leo chose to ignore what he thought was just an 'issue' and instead focused on healing himself from the toxicity he had fallen into.

However, for Leo, there was something strange about what he was feeling during those times. He began reminiscing about the moment Angela asked him for a picture;

then, as days passed, he started to miss her presence.

Leo then thought that perhaps he was just merely longing for genuine admiration, and missing someone he had just known and met was a pure hallucination. However, as the days went by, he came to realize he was wrong.

Eventually, he decided to follow his feelings. There could be another heartbreak waiting for him, but he no longer cared anyway. He took another risk, though he really thought Angela might have just been playing around, as someone as beautiful as her surely wouldn't become interested in someone like Leo.

He found a new reason to be excited to go to school after what had happened. He began smiling once again, which he had lost following the first heartbreak he ever experienced. Taking a glimpse of Angela wherever she passes by his classroom also became his routine. He now wishes to see her, even just for a moment, as that already completes his day.

Days went on, and Leo finally had the courage to make a move by messaging Angela on her social media account. This first move was then followed by little moments of conversation outside Angela's classroom during health break and lunch, which, unbeknownst to Angela, always makes Leo's heart pound fast.

Feelings grew deeper, and Leo eventually fell in love with her. He was aware that his first relationship was a failure, which he never wanted to experience again. But then he felt there was something about Angela that was worth the risk, worth a try, worth the courage, worth a heart, and so, just before the year ended, he asked Angela's father for permission and courted her.

It was on 25 April 2020, Angela's 18th birthday, when they made their

relationship official. Despite the challenging circumstances caused by the sudden outbreak of the virus and the country being under lockdown, which had started just a month earlier, it never affected their relationship.

Leo trusts her a lot, and he's certain that he has never loved anyone else the way he loves Angela. She's perfect and apparently one of Leo's inspirations in life. She made him feel grateful once again, accepted him, and made him feel like his existence mattered. Because of this, Leo further promised that he would never break her heart, as he knows Angela is truly worth loving.

Leo, upon seeing that there were people on Facebook humorously posting such research proposals for the ones they loved, decided to make his own version as well. Then, on their first anniversary on 25 April 2021, Leo posted his proposal on his Facebook account as a gift for his girlfriend, Angela.

Three years after posting his first research proposal, Leo then went on and tried a different topic, which he wanted to be something related to their four strong years of being together, thereby drafting his second proposal, which aims to determine the impact of strengthening trust, respect, and communication in Leo and Angela's relationship dynamics.

This proposal, then, is a remake of what Leo had created four years ago, serving as one of his gifts to his girlfriend, Angela, for their fourth anniversary on April 25, 2024.

Review of Related Literature

Numerous studies have found that strengthening trust, respect, and communication in a relationship is crucial for a long-term bond between partners

(Markman, Stanley, & Blumberg, 2010; Gottman & Silver, 2015; Fletcher et al., 2019).

Simpson and Winterheld (2018) have noted that trust is a multifaceted concept that serves as a cornerstone for relationship satisfaction and stability, playing a crucial role in fostering intimacy and building mutual respect in various types of relationships.

Respect, on the other hand, helps to build and maintain a strong connection between people (Exline, Elison, & Baumeister, 2012). However, respectful interactions are not just courteous gestures; they are also fundamental to relationship well-being and contribute significantly to the longevity and quality of relationships.

Furthermore, according to Folger, Poole, and Stutman (2017), open communication plays a crucial role in fostering better understanding and deeper connections between partners. It helps them feel heard and valued, which in turn promotes a sense of belonging and security within the relationship. They further highlighted that open communication is not just about talking but also about listening and understanding each other's perspectives.

Trust, respect, and communication are interconnected pillars that support a healthy relationship (Goodboy, Bolkan, & Shin, 2021). They create a strong foundation, fostering mutual understanding, intimacy, and growth between partners.

Conceptual Framework

The theory anchored in the context of relationship dynamics is the principle of social exchange theory. According to this theory, relationships are essentially a series of transactions where individuals assess the potential benefits and risks involved in interacting with each other (Gorman, 2020). This assessment then guides their

decisions and behaviors within the relationship. In this context, trust, respect, and communication are fundamental elements that influence these exchanges.

Social exchange theory suggests that trust, which involves believing in the reliability and integrity of the other person, is essential for the smooth functioning of relationships (Gottman & Silver, 2015). In the context of social exchange, trusting someone means believing that they will reciprocate your positive actions with positive actions of their own.

Similarly, respect, which is about valuing the other person's opinions, feelings, and boundaries, is related to social exchange, where showing respect can lead to mutual respect, further strengthening the relationship. When partners respect each other, they are more likely to continue beneficial exchanges (Johnson, 2022).

On the same side, effective communication is vital for expressing needs, concerns, and desires. Clear and open communication can help resolve conflicts, build trust, and foster mutual respect (Guerrero, Andersen, & Afifi, 2020). In social exchange, good communication ensures that partners understand the terms of the exchange and can negotiate effectively.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 illustrates the paradigm of the study, showcasing the relationship between the independent variable, strengthened TRRECO, and the dependent variable, Leo and Angela's relationship dynamics.

This means that, within the framework of this study, the level or quality of strengthened TRRECO will always have an impact on Leo and Angela's relationship, which can manifest in various ways: it could positively enhance their relationship by fostering trust, respect, and communication, or it could lead to changes in their relationship dynamics.

These changes could involve shifts in their interactions, emotional connection, or overall satisfaction with the relationship.

Research Questions

This study will be conducted in order to determine the impact of strengthening trust, respect, and communication in Leo and Angela's relationship dynamics.

Specifically, this study will seek answers to the following questions:

1. How may Leo and Angela's relationship dynamics be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. Trust?
 - 1.2. Respect?
 - 1.3. Communication?
2. To what extent can Leo's trust in Angela be described?
3. To what extent can Leo's respect for Angela be described?
4. Is there a significant relationship between strengthened TRRECO and Leo and Angela's relationship dynamics?

5. What are Leo and Angela's views on the concept of giving constant updates to one another?

Hypothesis

This study will be guided and tested by this hypothesis:

Ho: There is no significant relationship between strengthened TRRECO and Leo and Angela's relationship dynamics.

Significance of the Study

This study aims to determine the impact of strengthening trust, respect, and communication in Leo and Angela's relationship dynamics. The findings, then, may be beneficial to the couple, since trust, respect, and communication are among the foundations of a healthy relationship.

Moreover, the results of the study may be significant for the following:

John Leo L. Pilit. The findings of this study will be helpful for Leo, especially in considering the extent to which he trusts and respects his partner, Angela. The findings could also contribute to the ongoing establishment of their healthy relationship, and stronger communication could be utilized to avoid minor conflicts that may lead to arguments or discomfort.

Ma. Angela C. Pineda. The findings of this study will be helpful for Leo, especially in considering the extent to which he trusts and respects his partner, Angela. The findings could also contribute to the ongoing establishment of their healthy relationship, and stronger communication could be utilized to avoid minor conflicts that

may lead to arguments or discomfort.

Future Researchers. This research can be used as a guide by future researchers who are planning to take their research to the next level. Besides, the researcher followed the structure he learned from school, so be it a paper for educational purposes or just simply an idea similar to this, the format and structure itself can be trusted.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study primarily focuses on the impact of strengthening trust, respect, and communication in Leo and Angela's relationship dynamics and will not cover up other factors more than the specified ones.

A descriptive-correlational mixed-method research design with the aim of both describing a phenomenon or group and examining relationships between variables will be utilized in the conduct of this study, which will run from April 25 to November 25, 2024.

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